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Optically stimulated luminescence dating of loess in South-Eastern China using quartz and polymineral fine grains --Manuscript Draft--

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Abstract:	<p>Loess deposits distributed in southeastern China play an important role for paleoclimate reconstruction of the subtropical regions. These loess-paleosol deposits are mainly spread within the middle and lower reaches of the Yangtze River as well as in the drainage area of the Huai River. The ages of loess palaeosol sequences that are distributed along the Huai River are not well constrained. In this study, the standard single-aliquot regenerative dose (SAR) optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) protocol and two elevated temperature post infrared infrared stimulated luminescence protocols (pIRIR225 and pIRIR290) were applied on 4-11 μm quartz and polymineral fine grains, respectively, in order to obtain the first numerical luminescence chronology for a loess-paleosol sequence in northern Jiangsu Province. Our results show a good agreement between quartz SAR-OSL and polymineral pIRIR ages up to ~70 ka. These findings confirm that Xiashu loess accumulated during the Last Glaciation. For samples older than this, the ages obtained using the different methods do no longer agree within uncertainties. Fine quartz ages older than 70 ka are interpreted as underestimates, as previous studies reported this behavior on samples of various sedimentary origins worldwide. On the other hand, the pIRIR ages are most likely overestimating the true depositional ages as indicated by the results of dose recovery tests, where a 30-60 % overestimation of the recovered dose is reported for values larger than ~400 Gy. The overestimation of pIRIR protocols was also confirmed by the results obtained when large beta doses were added on top of the natural accrued dose. Moreover, our dating results revealed a mismatch between magnetic susceptibility enhancement and luminescence ages at MIS 5/4 boundary. This disagreement can be assigned to invalidity of magnetic susceptibility as a chronostratigraphical proxy due to ferrimagnetic minerals dissolution or transformation during pedogenesis process in this humid subtropical region in the southeastern China.</p>
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March 4th, 2021

TO THE EDITORIAL BOARD OF QUATERNARY GEOCHRONOLOGY JOURNAL,

Dear Professor Frank Preusser,

Please find enclosed the manuscript entitled "Optically stimulated luminescence dating of loess in South-Eastern China using quartz and polymineral fine grains".

Our study presents the application of the SAR-OSL protocol on fine quartz as well as two elevated temperature post-infrared infrared (pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀) protocols on polymineral fine grains extracted from a loess-paleosol sequence from southeastern China. This loess-paleosol profile makes part from *Xiashu* loess which is not completely studied. The aim of this work is to establish the first multi-method numerical chronology for Xuyi (XY) loess profile by comparing three sets of OSL ages with the magnetic susceptibility record.

Our age results exhibit agreement up to 70 ka for quartz SAR-OSL and polymineral pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀. For older ages, fine quartz underestimates the true depositional age as previous studies reported so far. In order to check the reliability of the pIRIR ages for samples older than 70 ka, various analyses have been carried out. Firstly, a dose recovery test has been applied on bleached polymineral fine grains aliquots. Further, a dose recovery test was carried out on fresh polymineral aliquots of a young sample by giving known beta doses on top of the natural dose. Moreover, considering the latest suggestion that a satisfactory pIRIR₂₉₀ dose recovery ratio is obtained when a test dose between 20-80% of D_e is used, a DRT was performed on pIRIR₂₉₀ protocol by varying the magnitude of the test dose. The dose recovery results have shown that for equivalent doses larger than ~400 Gy, both pIRIR protocols overestimate the expected dose by 30-60%. These findings were also supported by the fact that by giving dose of 5000 Gy on top of the natural accrued dose resulted in a signal that overestimates the saturation level of the pIRIR dose response curve by 11% and 18%, respectively.

By discussing the overall chronological dataset in light of the magnetic susceptibility data, this study demonstrates that a numerically dated timescale is crucial in future research of the *Xiashu* loess deposits.

We believe that our contribution will be of interest for quaternary geochronologists in general and to users and specialists involved in luminescence dating.

Please address any further correspondence related to this work to Anca Avram (anca.avram92@gmail.com).

Gratefully,

Anca Avram and the co-authors

Highlights

- First multi-method luminescence chronology for a loess profile in SE China
- Single Aliquot Regenerative dose protocol on 4-11 μm quartz
- Two elevated temperature post infrared-infrared protocols on polymineral fine grains
- Age agreement between protocols up to ~ 70 ka
- For doses larger than ~ 400 Gy post infrared-infrared protocols overestimate

1 Optically stimulated luminescence dating of loess in South-Eastern
2 China using quartz and polymineral fine grains

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13
14 **Abstract**

15 Loess deposits distributed in southeastern China play an important role for
16 paleoclimate reconstruction of the subtropical regions. These loess-paleosol deposits
17 are mainly spread within the middle and lower reaches of the Yangtze River as well
18 as in the drainage area of the Huai River. The ages of loess palaeosol sequences that
19 are distributed along the Huai River are not well constrained. In this study, the
20 standard single-aliquot regenerative dose (SAR) optically stimulated luminescence
21 (OSL) protocol and two elevated temperature post infrared infrared stimulated
22 luminescence protocols (pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀) were applied on 4-11 μm quartz and
23 polymineral fine grains, respectively, in order to obtain the first numerical

24 luminescence chronology for a loess-paleosol sequence in northern Jiangsu Province.
25 Our results show a good agreement between quartz SAR-OSL and polymineral
26 pIRIR ages up to ~70 ka. These findings confirm that *Xiashu* loess accumulated
27 during the Last Glaciation. For samples older than this, the ages obtained using the
28 different methods do no longer agree within uncertainties. Fine quartz ages older
29 than 70 ka are interpreted as underestimates, as previous studies reported this
30 behavior on samples of various sedimentary origins worldwide. On the other hand,
31 the pIRIR ages are most likely overestimating the true depositional ages as indicated
32 by the results of dose recovery tests, where a 30-60 % overestimation of the
33 recovered dose is reported for values larger than ~400 Gy. The overestimation of
34 pIRIR protocols was also confirmed by the results obtained when large beta doses
35 were added on top of the natural accrued dose. Moreover, our dating results
36 revealed a mismatch between magnetic susceptibility enhancement and
37 luminescence ages at MIS 5/4 boundary. This disagreement can be assigned to
38 invalidity of magnetic susceptibility as a chronostratigraphical proxy due to
39 ferrimagnetic minerals dissolution or transformation during pedogenesis process in
40 this humid subtropical region in the southeastern China.

41

42 **Keywords**

43 southeastern China, luminescence dating, quartz OSL, post-IR IRSL, polymineral
44 fine grains, loess

45

46 1. Introduction

47 The thick loess deposits of the Chinese Loess Plateau are regarded as an important
48 terrestrial archive that can provide information on the regional and global
49 paleoclimate changes, as these loess-paleosol sequences allow a secure correlation
50 with the marine oxygen isotopic record (**Heller and Liu, 1982, 1984, 1986**). In the
51 recent years, the widespread loess deposits to the south of the Chinese Loess
52 Plateau, distributed in the subtropical region of East Asia (**Jiang et al., 2020**) have
53 received noticeable attention due to the well-preserved paleoclimate records (**Hao et**
54 **al., 2010**). These archives are widely spread in the middle and lower reaches of the
55 Yangtze River as well as in the Huai River region recording changes starting from
56 the Mid-Pleistocene Transition (**Qiao et al., 2003; X. Li et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2018**).
57 The loess-paleosol sequences occurring in this region are collectively termed as
58 “*Xiashu* loess” (**Han et al., 2019 and references therein**).

59 The *Xiashu* loess was extensively documented in order to reconstruct the subtropical
60 Quaternary paleoenvironment. Numerous studies have reported important
61 information about the grain size characteristics of these loess deposits (**Qiao et al.,**
62 **2003; Liu and Deng, 2014; Han et al., 2019; Jiang et al., 2020**), environmental
63 magnetism (**Zhang et al., 2007; Qiao et al., 2003**), isotopic composition (**Li et al.,**
64 **2007; Qiao et al., 2011; Hong et al., 2013; Liu et al., 2014**) and provenance (**Hao et al.,**
65 **2010; Wang et al., 2018; Han et al., 2019; Jiang et al., 2020**). However, the ages of
66 these loess-paleosol sequences are not very well documented (**Qiao et al., 2003; Han**

67 **et al., 2019**). A limited number of luminescence dating studies were reported so far
68 for *Xiashu* loess (**Lai et al., 2010; Yi et al., 2018**). Seven luminescence ages were
69 published for Zhenjiang loess sequence located to the east of Nanjing city, in Jiangsu
70 Province (**Watanuki and Tsukamoto, 2001; Watanuki et al., 2003**). They report that
71 fading corrected IR and post-IR blue-stimulated OSL signals underestimate the true
72 age of deposition, suggesting that the post-IR blue stimulated OSL is more reliable
73 for dating than the IR signals using polymineral grains. Another study (**Yi et al.,**
74 **2018 and references therein**) presented 17 fine grained IRSL ages showing that L1
75 loess layer from the Xujiachun Section near Nanjing formed during the last
76 glaciations, between 72 ka and 14 ka and the lowermost layer of the *Xiashu* loess can
77 be correlated with the L5 loess unit at the Luochuan deposited by ~500 ka. **Lai et al.**
78 **(2010)** have applied the SAR protocol on quartz extracted from nine samples
79 collected from Jiujiang area and four samples from Nanjing area. Based on their OSL
80 ages, they confirm that the first loess layer from both Nanjing and Jiujiang area was
81 accumulated during the Last Glaciation. A more recent study by **Yi et al. (2018)**
82 reported a high-resolution luminescence chronology for two sites Yizheng and
83 Maba, located in the vicinity of Yizheng city, northeastern Nanjing. They reported a
84 good agreement between quartz and K-feldspar ages measured using SAR-OSL and
85 pIRIR₂₉₀ protocols, up to 50 ka. For the older samples, quartz OSL ages
86 underestimate the depositional age because of signal saturation whereas pIRIR₂₉₀
87 ages agree with the expected ages (**Yi et al., 2018**).

88 Loess deposits that are distributed within the drainage area of the Huai River have
89 received very little attention so far. While a few studies attempted to identify the
90 potential provenance of dust within this area (e.g. Han et al., 2019; Jiang et al., 2020)
91 no luminescence chronology has been reported (Hao et al., 2010, Han et al., 2019;
92 Jiang et al., 2020). The aim of this study is to provide the first numerical chronology
93 for a loess-paleosol profile from Huai River valley, southeastern China. Therefore,
94 luminescence dating method using three protocols has been applied on quartz and
95 polymineral fine grains extracted from eight samples. Moreover, the three sets of
96 ages are compared with the magnetic susceptibility records as well as with the
97 lithological information.

98 2. Study area

99 The alluvial plain of the Huai River drainage represents the region with one of the
100 widest *Xiashu* loess distribution in southern China. In this region, the mean annual
101 temperature and precipitation is 14.7 °C and 1005.5 mm, respectively. The analysis
102 presented in this study were made on samples collected from a typical loess-paleosol
103 sequence located within the hilly region (mainly eastern end of Zhangba Hills) in the
104 drainage area of the Huai River (**Figure 1**); the investigated loess-paleosol profile is
105 termed here as Xuyi (XY) section (118° 39.361' E, 32° 50.990' N) (**Figure 1**) and is
106 located in the Xuyi county, the Jiangsu Province, southern China. The total exposure
107 of the sequence reaches a thickness of ~6 m.

108

109 **Figure 1.** Location of the loess-paleosol sequence investigated in this study is
 110 represented by star symbol (map source: www.d-maps.com).

111 Luminescence investigations were performed on eight samples. Based on field
 112 observations, four samples were collected from L1 loess layer, one sample from the
 113 paleosol S1, two samples from the S1/L1 and L2/S1 transitions, and one sample from
 114 the bottom of the section (**Figure 2**).

115 3. Experimental details

116 3.1 Lithology and magnetic susceptibility data

117 At the Xuyi (XY) section, two glacial units L1 and L2 as well as the interglacial
 118 pedocomplex S1 are easily identified, according to the information displayed in
 119 **Figure 2**. The whole section had experienced strong paedogenesis, and the

120 lithological division are made by relative changes in the paedogenic intensity. The
121 upper part of the section is represented by a 40 cm-thick light reddish brown
122 weathered loess. The modern soil (S0) is missing from this loess-paleosol sequence.
123 Within the next 1.4 m a gray reddish brown weakly developed soil can be observed
124 with a high content of organic materials, followed by a weathered loess layer,
125 containing ferromanganese nodules. The interval between 2.8 and 3.6 m is
126 constituted by a weakly weathered reddish-brown layer. This layer may represent
127 the upper part of paleosol S1. The paleosol S1 corresponding with the last
128 interglacial period (marine oxygen isotope stage 5e) was recorded in the XY section
129 between 3.60-4.55 m. This interval is represented by a red and strongly weathered
130 paleosol. The lowermost 1.3 m is represented by a reddish yellow weathered loess
131 layer L1 accumulated during the penultimate glaciation, followed by strongly
132 weathered regolith material mixed with rock debris, and the bed rock of the section
133 composed of basalt.

134

135 **Figure 2.** Stratigraphy and magnetic susceptibility (MS) records of Xuyi (XY) loess-
 136 paleosol sequence. The stratigraphical position of luminescence samples is displayed
 137 with circle symbols in the stratigraphical column.

138 The variations recorded in magnetic susceptibility for loess-paleosol deposits in the
 139 Chinese Loess Plateau reflect palaeo-environmental changes during glacial and
 140 interglacial periods. Thus, an enhancement of the ferromagnetic minerals in loess is
 141 correlated with the paedogenetic process which took place during interglacial
 142 periods. By contrast, the concentration of ferromagnetic minerals decreases
 143 considerably in the glacial periods. Therefore, the magnetic susceptibility variations
 144 can be correlated with deep-sea oxygen isotope records (e.g., Liu, 1985; An et al.,
 145 1991; Lu et al., 1999; Hao et al., 2012). The magnetic susceptibility (MS) analysis was
 146 carried out on 246 samples collected from the XY loess-paleosol sequence at a

147 resolution of 2.5 cm. The variations recorded in the low-field MS display crucial
148 information about the XY pedostratigraphy. The complete MS record is presented in
149 **Figure 2**. Two significant MS variations were recorded between 3.6 ($\sim 57.8\text{-}180.7 \times 10^{-8}$
150 m^3kg^{-1}) - 4.55 m ($\sim 96.1\text{-}922.5 \times 10^{-8} \text{ m}^3\text{kg}^{-1}$) and >5.8 m. The latter corresponds to the
151 bottom of the section where the bedrock is composed of basalt. Based on MS values,
152 the first peak can be regarded as the S1 pedocomplex. However, this information is
153 in opposition with the lithological information described above in accordance with
154 field observation. In order to assess this mismatch observed between lithological
155 information and magnetic susceptibility results, the optically stimulated
156 luminescence dating was applied.

157 **3.2 OSL dating**

158 **3.2.1 Sample preparation and measurement technique**

159 OSL samples were collected in stainless steel tubes and prepared under subdued red
160 light laboratory conditions. Sediment at the end of each tube was used for gamma
161 spectrometry analysis. Material from the inner part of the tubes was used for quartz
162 and polymineral fine grains extraction. The first step of sample preparation
163 consisted in a treatment with hydrochloric acid (10% concentration) and hydrogen
164 peroxide (30% concentration) in order to remove carbonates and organic matter,
165 respectively. Further, the sediment was separated by dry sieving in to finer ($<63 \mu\text{m}$)
166 and coarser ($>63 \mu\text{m}$) fractions. Due to the small amount of material larger than 63
167 μm , coarse fractions could not be obtained for analysis. Therefore, the finer fraction

168 was used for quartz and polymineral fine grains extraction. The fine (4-11 μm)
169 polymineral mixture was separated by Stokes settling followed by centrifugation in
170 distilled water (Frechen et al., 1996; Lang et al., 1996). Fine (4-11 μm) quartz fraction
171 was enriched by etching with hydrofluoric acid for 10 days. For measurements, both
172 fine quartz and polymineral grains were mounted on aluminium disks.

173 Luminescence investigations were performed using two TL/OSL Risø DA-20 readers
174 equipped with either classic or automated, detection and stimulation head (DASH)
175 (Lapp et al., 2015). Luminescence signal detection was made by using an EMI
176 9235QA and PDM 9107Q-AO-TTL-30 (160-630 nm) photomultiplier tubes (Thomsen
177 et al., 2006). Quartz signals were detected by 7.5-mm-thick Hoya U-340 UV filters
178 while for polymineral fine grain signals a blue filter combination (Schott BG39 +
179 Corning 7-59, with transmission between 320-460 nm) was used. Laboratory
180 irradiations were performed using the incorporated ^{90}Sr - ^{90}Y radioactive sources that
181 were calibrated with gamma-irradiated calibration quartz (Hansen et al., 2015).

182 3.2.2 Equivalent dose determination

183 Quartz equivalent doses (D_e) were determined using a standard single aliquot
184 regenerative dose (SAR) protocol (Murray and Wintle, 2000, 2003) outlined in Table
185 1. Optical stimulation was performed using blue light-emitting diodes for 40 s at 125
186 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The net continuous wave optically stimulated luminescence (CW-OSL) signal of
187 interest was integrated over the first 0.308 s of the decay curve with an early
188 background subtraction (Cunningham and Wallinga, 2010) based on the signal

189 observed over the 1.69-2.30 s interval of stimulation in order to reduce the influence
190 of slow and medium components. The OSL response to a test dose of 17 Gy was
191 used for sensitivity change correction. A preheat temperature of 220 °C for 10 s and a
192 cutheat of 180 °C were employed. A high-temperature bleach (at 280 °C for 40 s) was
193 performed at the end of each SAR cycle using blue diodes as stimulation source
194 (**Murray and Wintle, 2003**). The robustness of the SAR protocol was evaluated
195 through the intrinsic performance tests (recycling and recuperation) (**Murray and**
196 **Wintle, 2003**) incorporated in every measurement. In order to check the purity of the
197 quartz luminescence signals, an IR stimulation step was added prior to OSL
198 measurement in the last cycle of the SAR protocol (**Duller, 2003**). Recycling and IR
199 depletion ratios within 10% deviation from unity constituted the acceptance criteria
200 for aliquots that were used in equivalent dose determination. Recuperation ratio was
201 considered suitable if the value of the signal measured after a zero dose was less
202 than 2% of the natural signal.

203 Further analysis was focused in equivalent dose determination on polymineral fine
204 grains using two elevated temperature infrared stimulation methods based on SAR
205 procedure, namely the pIRIR₂₂₅ (**Roberts 2008; Buylaert et al., 2009; Wacha and**
206 **Frechen 2011; Vasiliniuc et al., 2012**) (**Table 1b**) and pIRIR₂₉₀ (**Buylaert et al., 2011a,**
207 **2012; Thiel et al., 2011a**) (**Table 1c**) protocols. In order to reduce the signal
208 susceptible to fading by allowing recombination of near-neighbour trap and centre
209 pairs, a stimulation with IR diodes for 200 s at 50 °C was performed after a preheat

210 of 250 °C (pIRIR₂₂₅) and 320 °C (pIRIR₂₉₀) for 60 s, respectively. The signal of interest
211 was recorded during a subsequent IR stimulation for 200 s at 225 °C and 290 °C,
212 respectively. The magnitude of the test dose was chosen taking into account the
213 magnitude of the equivalent doses, as following: for the uppermost two samples (XY
214 40 and XY 180) a test dose of 50 Gy was used while for the rest of the samples the
215 magnitude of the test dose was 75 Gy. The net signal used for analysis was
216 integrated from the initial 2.5 s of stimulation minus a background evaluated from
217 the last 50 s. A high temperature bleach was performed for 100 s at 290 °C (pIRIR₂₂₅)
218 and 325 °C (pIRIR₂₉₀) at the end of each cycle of measurements to remove residual
219 charge.

220 The aliquots used for residual dose and dose recovery measurements were bleached
221 under natural conditions on a window, in Cluj-Napoca, Romania (latitude 46° 47'
222 N).

223 3.2.3 Dosimetry

224 Radionuclide specific activities were determined using high resolution gamma
225 spectrometry. In order to achieve the ²²²Rn-²²⁶Ra equilibrium, the samples were
226 stored for 1 month before measurements. The total dose rates were derived based on
227 the conversion factors tabulated by **Guérin et al. (2011)**. An alpha efficiency factor of
228 0.04±0.02 was assumed for 4-11 µm quartz whereas for polymineral fine grains a
229 value of 0.08±0.02 was taken into account (**Rees-Jones, 1995**). The cosmic dose rate
230 was calculated according to the formula proposed by **Prescott and Hutton (1994)**.

231 The time averaged water content was assumed to be 15% with a relative error of
232 25%. The percentage used for water content was chosen to represent the mean value
233 of the sediment moisture over the entire depositional history. Similar water content
234 values were used for loess from nearby *Xiashu* profiles (e.g., **Watanuki et al., 2003;**
235 **Lai et al., 2010, Yi et al., 2018**). Any dose rate derived from internal alpha activity
236 was assumed that is negligibly small, given the size of fine grains (4-11 μm).
237 Information about uranium, thorium and potassium concentration as well as the
238 total dose rates are summarised in **Table 2**.

239 **4. Results and discussion**

240 **4.1 Luminescence characteristics**

241 **4.1.1 Quartz OSL**

242 The equivalent doses were obtained by interpolating the sensitivity corrected natural
243 OSL signal onto the dose response curve. Representative SAR growth curve and OSL
244 decay curves for a single aliquot of fine (4-11 μm) grained quartz from sample XY40
245 is shown in **Figure 3**. The natural OSL signal decayed significantly within the first
246 second of stimulation, exhibiting a similar pattern to that of the decay measured for
247 calibration quartz which is accepted as being dominated by the fast component
248 (**Hansen et al., 2015**). The dose response curve was best fitted using the sum of two
249 saturating exponential functions. Recycling and IR depletion ratios were within 10%
250 deviation from unity, indicating that the sensitivity changes during repeated SAR

251 cycles are corrected properly, and signals measured come from quartz. Recuperation
 252 ratio was less than 2%, indicating that the growth curves pass very close to the origin
 253 and that thermal transfer during SAR protocol is negligible.

254

255 **Figure 3.** Representative sensitivity-corrected dose response curves constructed for
 256 one aliquot of sample XY40 on 4-11 μm quartz using SAR-OSL protocol. The
 257 sensitivity corrected natural signals (stars) are interpolated on the dose response
 258 curves. IR depletion point is presented as an up triangle while the recycling points
 259 are presented as inverse triangles. The inset shows the pattern of a typical quartz
 260 decay curve which is compared with the decay of a regenerative dose as well as with
 261 the OSL decay of calibration quartz.

262 Further, a preheat plateau test was employed in order to investigate the dependency
263 of the equivalent doses on the preheat temperature. Aliquots of fine quartz grains
264 from samples XY180 and XY260 were divided in groups of five, each corresponding
265 to a temperature point (180 °C, 220 °C, 240 °C, 260 °C and 280 °C). A cutheat to 180
266 °C was employed throughout the measurements. As shown in **Figure 4**, the
267 observed equivalent doses display no significant variations for thermal treatments
268 between 180 °C and 280 °C suggesting that the equivalent dose values are
269 independent of preheat temperatures and validating the choice of a 220 °C preheat
270 temperature.

271

272 **Figure 4.** Equivalent dose dependence on preheat temperatures for 4-11 μm quartz
273 for samples XY180 and XY260. A cutheat (test dose preheat) of 180 °C was
274 employed.

275 To test the reliability of the equivalent doses obtained using the SAR protocol, a dose
276 recovery test (Murray and Wintle, 2003) was performed on six samples (XY180,
277 XY260, XY340, XY400, XY460 and XY575). Aliquots of fine quartz grains were
278 bleached twice for 250 s at room temperature using blue LEDs. A pause of 10 ks was
279 included between the stimulation. Each aliquot was then irradiated with a known
280 laboratory dose chosen to approximate the natural dose. The aliquots were
281 measured by applying the SAR protocol in the same manner as measuring the
282 equivalent dose. As shown in Figure 5, dose recovery ratios were satisfactory for all
283 samples documented here, indicating that laboratory doses up to 474 Gy given prior
284 to any heat treatment are accurately measured using the SAR protocol.

285

286 **Figure 5.** The results of dose recovery test for 4-11 μm quartz extracted from samples
287 XY180, XY260, XY340, XY400, XY460 and XY575.

288 The measured quartz OSL equivalent doses along with the results of the intrinsic
289 tests of SAR protocol are presented in Supplementary file (**Table S1**). For each
290 sample, 10 replicate measurements of the equivalent dose were performed. None of
291 the aliquots investigated in this study were rejected due to the poor performance of
292 the intrinsic tests (recycling, IR depletion and recuperation), which assert the good
293 luminescence behaviour of the quartz extracted from all samples.

294 **4.1.2 Polymineral fine grains – pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀**

295 The equivalent doses measured on polymineral fine grains were obtained in the
296 same manner as those obtained from fine quartz by applying pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀
297 protocols using between eight to twelve aliquots for each sample. Representative
298 growth curves for sample XY180 constructed using pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ protocols
299 are shown in **Figure 6a and b**. The growth curves pass very close to the origin
300 indicating that the recuperation is insignificant. The insets of **Figure 6a and b** show
301 the similar shapes of the natural and regenerative signals decay curves. The
302 measured pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ equivalent doses together with the results of the
303 recycling and recuperation values are presented in Supplementary file (**Table S2**).

a.

b.

304 **Figure 6.** Representative sensitivity-corrected dose response curves constructed for
 305 one aliquot of sample XY180 on (a) 4-11 μm polymineral fine grains using the
 306 pIRIR₂₂₅ protocol and (b) 4-11 μm polymineral using pIRIR₂₉₀ protocol. The
 307 sensitivity corrected natural signals (stars) are interpolated on the dose response
 308 curves. The recycling points are presented as inverse triangles. Insets show typical
 309 decay curves. For polymineral fine grains, the natural CW-OSL signals are compared

310 to regenerated signals induced by a beta dose approximately equal to the equivalent
311 dose.

312 *Residual doses*

313 One of the main assumptions of luminescence dating is that the sediment is fully-
314 bleached in nature prior to deposition and burial. Existing studies have shown that
315 pIRIR signals are more difficult to bleach and an un-bleachable component in the
316 range of 4-7 Gy exists ubiquitously in fully-bleached samples (**Buylaert et al., 2012;**
317 **Sohbati et al., 2012; Murray et al., 2014; Li et al., 2016**). Several studies reported
318 residual doses for pIRIR_{225/290} signals that can vary within a wide range from a few
319 Gy (<2 Gy) to >40 Gy (**Thiel et al., 2011a; Buylaert et al., 2011a,b; Wacha and**
320 **Frechen 2011; Vasiliniuc et al., 2012; Stevens et al., 2011; Murray et al., 2014; Y. Li et**
321 **al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2018; Veres et al., 2018, Yi et al., 2018; Avram et al., 2020**).
322 Moreover, a dependency between the residual doses and equivalent doses was
323 observed in several depositional environments (**Buylaert et al., 2012; Sohbati et al.,**
324 **2012; Kars et al., 2014; Li et al., 2016, 2017; Yi et al., 2016**). Long-term bleaching
325 experiments using pIRIR₂₉₀ protocol were conducted by **Yi et al. (2016; 2018)** on loess
326 samples from northeastern and southeastern China, respectively. They have shown
327 that a constant residual dose of $\sim 6 \pm 1$ Gy and $\sim 4 \pm 1$ Gy is reached after ~ 300 h
328 bleaching in a Hönle SOL2 simulator.

329 For pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ residual dose measurements, sets of five aliquots from each
330 sample were used. The aliquots were first bleached for 30 days under natural

331 condition by exposure to window light. The residual doses are displayed as function
332 of equivalent dose in **Figure 7** and **Table S3**. The magnitude of the remanent doses
333 measured using pIRIR₂₂₅ protocol range from 2.0 ± 0.1 to 9 ± 1 Gy while the pIRIR₂₉₀
334 residual doses are larger and vary between 4 ± 1 and 19 ± 3 Gy. Moreover, these results
335 show a dependency between the residual dose and the equivalent dose values
336 (**Figure 7**). These values were subtracted from all pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ equivalent
337 doses before the age calculation. The final equivalent doses used for age
338 determination are shown in **Table 2**.

339

340 **Figure 7.** Residual doses measured after an exposure of 30 days to window light as
341 function of measured equivalent doses.

342

343 *Dose recovery test*

344 A rigorous test that can provide information on the accuracy of the measurement
345 protocols used is the dose recovery test (Murray 1996; Wallinga et al., 2000). Even
346 though some studies reported acceptable results for dose recovery tests when using
347 pIRIR₂₉₀ protocol on feldspars of various sedimentary origins (e.g. Buylaert et al.,
348 2011, 2012, 2013; Thiel et al., 2012; Sohbaty et al., 2016; Yi et al., 2016, 2018; Böskén
349 et al., 2017; Stevens et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2018), unsatisfactory dose recovery
350 results were also reported (e.g., Stevens et al., 2011; Thiel et al., 2011b; Murray et
351 al., 2014; Y. Li et al., 2018; Veres et al., 2018; Avram et al., 2020). In contrast to the
352 results on pIRIR₂₉₀ protocol, most studies reported good dose recovery ratios when
353 using the pIRIR₂₂₅ protocol (e.g., Y. Li et al., 2018; Avram et al., 2020). Some studies
354 suggested that the dose recovery ratio is dependent on the size of the test dose when
355 pIRIR₂₉₀ protocol is used (Qin and Zhou, 2012; Yi et al., 2016, 2018). Yi et al. (2016)
356 concluded that a test dose between 15 and 80% of the total dose is the best choice for
357 obtaining a good dose recovery ratio. On the other hand, Avram et al. (2020)
358 reported a poor dose recovery ratio using a test dose of 41% of the given dose on
359 polymineral fine grains extracted from Serbian loess.

360 In order to check if both pIRIR protocols can successfully recover a known
361 laboratory given dose, sets of five aliquots from samples XY40, XY100, XY180,
362 XY260, XY400 and XY460 were bleached under natural conditions by exposure to
363 window light for 30 days. Given laboratory doses of 88 Gy for pIRIR₂₂₅ and 96 Gy for

364 pIRIR₂₉₀ were chosen for sample XY40 while sample XY100 was irradiated with beta
365 doses of 135 Gy in the case of pIRIR₂₂₅ protocol and 143 Gy for the application of the
366 pIRIR₂₉₀ protocol. For the other samples, the magnitude of given doses were chosen
367 as follows: for dose recovery test measured using pIRIR₂₂₅ protocol three sets of five
368 aliquots from sample XY180 were irradiated with beta doses of 400 Gy, 600 Gy and
369 800 Gy while for dose recovery test using pIRIR₂₉₀ protocol, sample XY260 was
370 irradiated with a beta dose of 200 Gy, for sample XY400 a dose of 400 Gy was used
371 and for XY460 sample, five aliquots were given a dose of 600 Gy and five aliquots
372 were irradiated with a dose of 745 Gy. The test doses used throughout these dose
373 recovery measurements were the same as in equivalent dose determination. The
374 residual doses were subtracted before dose recovery ratio calculation. The dose
375 recovery ratios for pIRIR₂₂₅ protocol were 1.02 ± 0.05 for sample XY40 while for
376 sample XY100 a dose recovery ratio of 1.06 ± 0.03 was obtained. For higher given
377 doses (> 400 Gy), dose recovery ratios start to overestimate by ~ 20 - 40% (**Figure 8a**).
378 In the case of pIRIR₂₉₀ protocol, dose recovery ratios of $\sim 1.12 \pm 0.04$ were obtained for
379 given doses up to 200 Gy while for doses higher than 400 Gy, dose recovery ratios
380 overestimate unity by ~ 30 to 60% (**Figure 8b**).

381 Furthermore, the dependency of the dose recovery ratios on the magnitude of the
382 test dose was checked for pIRIR₂₉₀ protocol. Five aliquots from sample XY100 and
383 XY575 were irradiated with a beta dose chosen to approximate the measured
384 equivalent doses and the magnitude of the test dose used was 17 Gy. Poor dose

385 recovery ratios were obtained for both XY100 (1.19 ± 0.03) and XY575 (1.23 ± 0.02)
 386 samples (**Figure 8b**). These results show that the magnitude of the test dose does not
 387 influence the dose recovery ratio for pIRIR₂₉₀ protocol.

388
 389 **Figure 8.** The results of dose recovery test on 4-11 μm polymineral bleached aliquots
 390 using: (a) pIRIR₂₂₅ protocol for samples XY40, XY100, XY180 and (b) pIRIR₂₉₀ protocol
 391 for samples XY40, XY100, XY260, XY400, XY460 and XY575; and the dose recovery
 392 test results when the given doses were added on top of natural dose from sample
 393 XY40 using (c) pIRIR₂₂₅ and (d) pIRIR₂₉₀ protocols. The measured equivalent dose of
 394 sample XY40 using pIRIR₂₂₅ protocol was ~101 Gy while using pIRIR₂₉₀ protocol was
 395 ~ 97 Gy. Different symbols denote the use of different test dose values.

396 Because of the hard to bleach component of the pIRIR natural signals (e.g., **Thomsen**
397 **et al., 2008; Buylaert et al., 2012, Yi et al., 2016, 2018**), some previous studies
398 suggested that the incorrect estimation of residual dose can lead to poor dose
399 recovery ratios (**Stevens et al., 2011; Alexanderson and Murray, 2012**). In order to
400 avoid the potential complications due to inaccurate residual dose estimation, a dose
401 recovery test can be performed by adding different beta doses on top of the natural
402 signal of a young sample. The dose recovery ratios are further calculated by dividing
403 the measured dose with the sum of the natural (i.e., previously determined
404 equivalent dose) and the additional given dose (**Buylaert et al., 2011b, Yi et al.,**
405 **2018**).

406 In this study, the uppermost sample XY 40 (measured D_e of ~97 Gy using pIRIR₂₉₀
407 protocol and ~101 Gy using pIRIR₂₂₅ protocol) was chosen and beta doses of 103, 303,
408 503 and 703 Gy as well as 99, 299, 499 and 699 Gy were added on top of the natural
409 signals when pIRIR₂₉₀ and pIRIR₂₂₅ protocols were used. As such, the dose recovery
410 test was carried out for doses ranging from 200 to 800 Gy. The dose recovery ratios
411 increase from 1.10 ± 0.04 for a total dose (natural+given dose) of 200 Gy to 1.71 ± 0.08
412 for a dose of 800 Gy for pIRIR₂₂₅ protocol (**Figure 8c**). In the case of pIRIR₂₉₀ protocol
413 the dose recovery ratios increase from 1.12 ± 0.03 for a total dose (natural+given dose)
414 of 200 Gy to 1.60 ± 0.06 for a total dose of 800 Gy (**Figure 8d**). This confirms our
415 previous observations in the dose recovery experiment performed using bleached
416 aliquots. These results suggest that doses up to 200-300 Gy can be accurately

417 measured with both pIRIR protocols while doses larger than 400 Gy are
418 overestimated. In contrast with these results, **Yi et al., (2018)** reported good dose
419 recovery ratios for pIRIR₂₉₀ protocol for doses up to 700 Gy when beta doses were
420 added on top of the natural signal for a young sample from *Xiashu* loess.

421 *Fading*

422 The choice of feldspar minerals as dosimeter in luminescence dating has been so
423 long hampered by a phenomenon known as anomalous fading (**Wintle, 1973;**
424 **Spooner, 1992, 1994**). This phenomenon represents the loss of the stable
425 luminescence signal of feldspar under ambient temperature. It is suggested that the
426 IRSL signal from feldspar fades due to the quantum mechanical tunnelling between
427 the electron traps and holes (**Visocekas, 1985; Wintle, 1973; Spooner, 1992, 1994**).
428 The percentage of the signal lost per decade can be measured in term of fading rates
429 (**Aitken 1985**). In the last years, several studies have focused on the development of
430 some fading correction methods (**Huntley and Lamothe, 2001; Lamothe et al., 2003;**
431 **Kars et al., 2008**).

432 **Thiel et al., 2011** were the first who concluded that the pIRIR₂₉₀ signal is a stable
433 signal and the ages obtained using pIRIR₂₉₀ protocol do not need any further
434 correction for fading. This finding was also confirmed by some several other studies
435 (e.g **Stevens et al., 2011; Buylaert et al., 2011; Thomsen et al., 2011, Veres et al., 2018;**
436 **Avram et al., 2020**).

437 Therefore, fading tests were conducted only for the pIRIR₂₂₅ protocol. Four 4-11 μ m
438 polymineral aliquots of samples XY40, XY100 and XY340 were used for fading rates
439 measurements. The aliquots were first bleached for 21 days by exposure to window
440 light. Further, XY40 and XY100 samples were irradiated with a beta dose of 100 Gy
441 while for XY340 sample a dose of 300 Gy was used. The magnitude of the test dose
442 remained the same as in the equivalent dose measurements. Four consecutive read
443 outs were carried out prior to the fading measurement. Different storage time
444 ranging between 2 h and 50 days were used for samples XY40 and XY100 while for
445 sample XY340 a shorter storage time of 2 days was used. The aliquots were
446 preheated before storage. The results of each individual aliquot measured are
447 displayed in **Figure S1 and Table 3**. An average g-value smaller than 0.7 %/decade
448 was obtained for all samples investigated here. Similar fading rates of ~1%/decade
449 are considered to be laboratory artefacts by **Vasiliniuc et al. (2012)**. Moreover, a
450 recent study that documented fading rates measured on calibration quartz as well as
451 on polymineral fine grains using both pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ protocols, suggesting
452 that reliable g-values cannot be determined by short-term laboratory fading
453 measurements (**Avram et al., 2020**). Based on our results as well as on the findings
454 reported so far in literature, in the following sections the uncorrected pIRIR ages are
455 further discussed.

456 **4.1.3 Saturation characteristics of quartz and feldspars signal**

457 In order to assess the maximum equivalent dose that can be accurately measured by
458 each protocol, the saturation characteristics of the laboratory signals emitted by
459 quartz and feldspars should be identified. Previous studies showed that for
460 obtaining meaningful saturation parameters, the dose response curves need to be
461 constructed up to saturation (**Timar-Gabor and Wintle, 2013; Timar-Gabor et al.,**
462 **2017; Anechitei-Deacu et al., 2018**). Therefore, laboratory dose response curves up to
463 5000 Gy were constructed for 4-11 μm quartz and polymineral on sample XY575,
464 using SAR-OSL, pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ protocols (**Figure 9a**). All dose response curves
465 were well fitted by the sum of two saturating exponential functions:

$$466 \quad I = I_0 + a (1 - e^{-D/D_{01}}) + c (1 - e^{-D/D_{02}})$$

467 Where I represent the intensity of the signal for a dose D ; I_0 is the intercept, a and b
468 represent the amplitudes of the exponential functions while D_{01} and D_{02} denote the
469 saturation doses for each exponential function. We assume a saturation threshold of
470 85% of the saturation level of the signal, in other words the maximum level of the
471 signal reached when constructing the laboratory dose response (**Wintle and Murray,**
472 **2006**). In order to evaluate the closeness to saturation of sample XY575 with
473 equivalent doses >800 Gy, the ratios between the average sensitivity-corrected
474 luminescence signals ($L_{\text{nat}}/T_{\text{nat}}$) and the corrected luminescence signal measured for a
475 regenerative dose of 5000 Gy ($(L_x/T_x)_{5000 \text{ Gy}}$) were calculated. For fine quartz OSL
476 signals the natural signal is interpolated under the saturation threshold ($\sim 58 \pm 1\%$ of
477 the value obtained for 5000 Gy) (**Figure 9a**). The natural signal of sample XY575 is

478 interpolated onto the pIRIR₂₂₅ laboratory growth curve at 68±1% of the value
479 obtained at 5000 Gy (**Figure 9a**). In the case of pIRIR₂₉₀, the natural signal of sample
480 XY575 intersects the dose response curve at 81±3% of the saturation level (**Figure 9a**).
481 As such, the results obtained on samples XY575 should be considered reliable as
482 long as the closeness to saturation of the signals is concerned.

483 The laboratory dose response curve constructed on 4-11 µm quartz has characteristic
484 saturation doses of $D_{01} = 117 \pm 33$ Gy and $D_{02} = 1201 \pm 170$ Gy. Similar saturation
485 characteristics were determined on loess sample extracted from Chinese Loess
486 Plateau (**Timar-Gabor et al., 2017**). In the case of pIRIR₂₂₅ the saturation
487 characteristics of the dose response curve are $D_{01} = 175 \pm 15$ Gy and $D_{02} = 1094 \pm 53$ Gy
488 while for pIRIR₂₂₉ values of $D_{01} = 150 \pm 39$ Gy and $D_{02} = 795 \pm 98$ Gy were obtained, in
489 accordance to the previous results reported on polymineral fine grains extracted
490 from Serbian loess (**Avram et al., 2020**).

491 *High laboratory doses added on top of the natural signal*

492 Previous studies demonstrated that the application of the SAR-OSL procedure is
493 problematic in the high dose range (**Timar-Gabor et al., 2017; Anechitei et al., 2018,**
494 **Veres et al., 2018; Avram et al., 2020**). When large laboratory doses are added on top
495 of the naturally accrued doses, the magnitude of the measured signal is expected to
496 be at the same level as the saturation signal measured in the SAR procedure.

497 Such an experiment has been carried out on sample XY180 (equivalent dose of ~200
 498 Gy) on fine quartz and polymineral fine grains using SAR-OSL, pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀
 499 protocols. A large laboratory dose of 5000 Gy was given on top of the natural dose
 500 and the measured sensitivity corrected luminescence signal is further denoted as
 501 $(L_n/T_n)^*$. The same aliquots were subsequently measured in a standard SAR
 502 procedure up to 5000 Gy using to equal the equivalent dose plus the given dose. The
 503 measured sensitivity corrected luminescence signal at 5000 Gy is further denoted as
 504 (L_x/T_x) .

505

506 **Figure 9.** Laboratory dose response curves constructed for 4-11 μm quartz and
 507 polymineral grains measured using pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ protocols on sample
 508 XY575. All growth curves were best fitted by a sum of two saturating exponential
 509 functions. Each data point represents an average of three measurements. (a) The
 510 average natural sensitivity corrected luminescence signal (L_{nat}/T_{nat}) obtained on all
 511 aliquots measured; including the aliquots used for De measurements is represented.

512 The percentage indicated represents the ratio between the L_{nat}/T_{nat} and the L_x/T_x
 513 measured for a 5000 Gy regenerative dose. (b) The average natural+5000 Gy
 514 sensitivity corrected signals $(L_n/T_n)^*$ are interpolated onto the DRCs. The percentage
 515 indicate the ratio between the $(L_n/T_n)^*$ and the L_x/T_x measured for a regenerative dose
 516 of 5000 Gy.

517 In the case of fine quartz, the ratio between $(L_n/T_n)^*$ and (L_x/T_x) is 0.94 ± 0.04 (**Figure**
 518 **9b**). Similar ratios were previously reported when large doses were added on top of

519 the natural dose on fine quartz samples extracted from loess (Veres et al., 2018;
520 Avram et al., 2020) and aeolianites (Anehitei-Deacu et al., 2018).

521 The ratio between the $(L_n/T_n)^*$ and (L_x/T_x) in the case of pIRIR₂₂₅ is 1.11 ± 0.04 while
522 in the case of pIRIR₂₉₀ the ratio is 1.18 ± 0.09 (Figure 9b). Avram et al., (2020) also
523 reported a ratio of 1.10 ± 0.03 for pIRIR₂₂₅ and 1.15 ± 0.05 for pIRIR₂₉₀ on polymineral
524 fine grains extracted from Serbian loess.

525 These results are pointing out that for large doses fine quartz natural signal
526 underestimates the true depositional dose. In the case of pIRIR protocols, the result
527 ratios confirm the overestimation observed in dose recovery test (presented above)
528 indicating that the signals measured during the first measurement cycle slightly
529 overestimate the signal obtained for a dose with the same magnitude given later in
530 the SAR protocol. The pIRIR₂₉₀ overestimation is larger than in the case of pIRIR₂₂₅, as
531 previously reported.

532 4.2 Luminescence ages

533 The 4-11 μm quartz SAR-OSL and uncorrected 4-11 μm polymineral pIRIR₂₂₅ and
534 pIRIR₂₉₀ ages are presented in Figure 10 and Table 2. All three sets of ages are
535 generally in agreement with each other up to ~ 70 ka and no reversals occur.

536 For the time span when ages obtained using different methods agree quartz SAR-
537 OSL ages range from 22 ± 2 ka to 64 ± 6 ka. Beyond this limit, fine quartz ages start to
538 underestimate the true depositional age. Previous studies on quartz extracted from

539 European loess showed that fine grained quartz natural and laboratory growth
 540 curves overlap up to $\sim 150 - 200$ Gy, suggesting that the upper limit of SAR-based
 541 fine quartz OSL dating is ~ 50 ka (Timar-Gabor and Wintle, 2013; Avram et al.,
 542 2020). Similar results were obtained by Chapot et al., 2012 for 35-63 μm quartz
 543 extracted from Chinese loess. Moreover, in the study reported by Lai (2010) on loess
 544 from Louchuan profile (CLP), their quartz ages start to underestimate the true age
 545 starting from ~ 70 ka.

546 The pIRIR ages are consistent with each other up to 70 ka. In the case of pIRIR₂₂₅
 547 protocol, ages from 21 ± 2 ka to 70 ± 6 ka were obtained while pIRIR₂₉₀ ages range from
 548 23 ± 2 ka to 69 ± 6 ka.

549

550 **Figure 10.** Magnetic susceptibility record and the three sets of ages obtained on
551 quartz and polymineral fine grains using SAR-OSL and pIRIR protocols,
552 respectively presented as function of depth.

553 For samples XY340 downwards the feldspar derived ages overestimate the
554 chronological information obtained using quartz. The results of the dose recovery
555 test as well as those obtained when a high beta dose is added on top of the natural
556 dose have shown that for doses larger than 200-300 Gy, the pIRIR protocol starts to
557 overestimate the given dose. Thus, we interpret these ages as overestimates. A recent
558 study on polymineral fine grains extracted from Serbian loess compared the natural
559 and laboratory dose response curves constructed by applying pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀
560 protocols, respectively. They showed that pIRIR₂₂₅ natural and laboratory curves
561 overlap up to at least ~500 Gy while in the case of pIRIR₂₉₀ they overlap up to 400 Gy
562 beyond which the natural signals overestimate the laboratory signal. Moreover, they
563 suggested that equivalent doses larger than this interval to be interpreted with
564 caution (Avram et al., 2020).

565 Based on the results obtained in this study, we are confident that the three sets of
566 ages on quartz and polymineral fine grains are reliable up to ~70 ka. Beyond this
567 interval, the quartz SAR-OSL ages should be regarded as underestimated whereas
568 polymineral pIRIR ages slightly overestimate the true depositional age.

569 **4.3 Chronostratigraphical interpretation**

570 As shown in **Figure 10** the OSL ages for the uppermost part of the section (up to a
571 depth of 260 cm) revealed that the aeolian sediment deposited along the drainage
572 area of the Huai River was accumulated during the last glaciation. Previous
573 luminescence chronology reported on *Xiashu* loess straighten our findings (**Yi et al.,**
574 **2018 and references therein**). Therefore, this part of the section can be correlated
575 with the L1 loess layer observed in the Chinese Loess Plateau (**Liu 1985**) and thus
576 with the marine isotope stages (MIS) 2-4 (**Lisiecky and Raymo, 2005**).

577 The S1/L1 as well as L2/S1 transitions for CLP was established at ~71 ka and 128 ka,
578 respectively by climatic correlation to the well-established chronology in the marine
579 sediments (**Imbrie et al., 1984**). The enhancement observed in MS data (**Figure 2**),
580 between 340 and 460 cm, suggest the presence of a very strong S1 pedocomplex and
581 thus the S1/L1 transition can be assigned based on this data to a depth of 340 cm. For
582 this sample, an age of 118 ± 10 ka was obtained by the application of the pIRIR₂₂₅
583 protocol, corresponding to MIS 5. However, as mentioned above, the ages for
584 samples older than 70 ka should be regarded with caution and therefore we cannot
585 assess accurately the S1/L1 transition recorded in the XY loess-paleosol section. Ages
586 obtained using the pIRIR₂₂₅ method for samples XY400, XY 460 and XY 575 using the
587 pIRIR₂₂₅ protocol are 140 ± 13 ka (corresponding within error to MIS 5), 162 ± 15 and
588 205 ± 19 ka respectively, corresponding within error to MIS 6. For the pIRIR₂₉₀ protocol
589 values of 182 ± 19 ka, 211 ± 19 ka and 228 ± 24 ka, respectively, were obtained. However,
590 as explained above, based on the results of the dose recovery test these ages should

591 be regarded as overestimating the true depositional age. As such, in order to
592 establish a robust chronology for older sediments for the drainage area of the Huai
593 River, southern China, more analysis are needed.

594 The mismatch between changes in magnetic susceptibility and luminescence dating
595 at MIS 4/5 boundary in the XY section suggest that caution should be taken when
596 developing a timescale of *Xiashu* loess deposits based on correlation with the marine
597 oxygen isotope record. This correlation approach has been widely employed in
598 establishment of chronology for the European loess deposits (e.g., **Hao et al., 2012;**
599 **Marković et al., 2015; Zeeden et al., 2018; Schaetzl et al., 2018**). The fundamental
600 premise for this correlation-based time scale is that the boundary of glacial loess
601 layer and interglacial paleosol is consistent with that of the magnetic susceptibility.
602 However, as stated in the aforementioned text, upper part of S1 between depth of
603 280 cm and 350 cm are characterized by low values of magnetic susceptibility
604 (**Figure 2 and Figure 10**). If adopting the midpoint between the start and end of an
605 interval of rapid increase in magnetic susceptibility as the tie point of age, the MIS
606 4/5 boundary in susceptibility curve will be assigned to depth of 365 cm of the XY
607 section. This is serious lower than the boundary around at depth of 280 cm achieved
608 by luminescence dating (**Figure 10**). This significant mismatch demonstrates serious
609 uncertainty in development of the susceptibility-correlation-based chronology for
610 the *Xiashu* loess. Dissolution and transformation of the ferrimagnetic minerals
611 during the pedogenesis and/or after burial in the humid subtropical southern China

612 may be reason for invalidity magnetic susceptibility as a stratigraphic tool in *Xiashu*
613 loess. Therefore, this study demonstrate that a numerically dated timescale is crucial
614 in future research of the *Xiashu* loess deposits.

615 **5. Conclusion**

616 High-resolution luminescence dating on 4-11 μm quartz and polymineral grains
617 using SAR-OSL, pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ protocols have been applied on *Xiashu* loess
618 deposits accumulated within the drainage area of the Huai River in southern China.
619 Luminescence characteristics of quartz as well as of polymineral grains displayed a
620 good behaviour in the SAR procedure for doses up to ~300 Gy. Luminescence ages
621 obtained on fine quartz using SAR-OSL protocol and on polymineral fine grains
622 using pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ protocols are consistent with each other up to ~70 ka, and
623 thus confirming that the first layer of aeolian dust within the investigated region was
624 accumulated during the last Glaciation. For samples with higher equivalent doses,
625 the SAR-OSL protocol applied on quartz underestimate the true depositional ages
626 whereas the ages obtained using both pIRIR protocols are interpreted as
627 overestimate, an interpretation supported by the results obtained in dose recovery
628 tests.

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step	a. SAR protocol	b. pIRIR ₂₉₀	c. pIRIR ₂₂₅
1	Dose	Dose	Dose
2	Preheat (220 °C; 10s)	Preheat (320 °C; 60s)	Preheat (250 °C; 60s)
3	Blue OSL (125 °C; 40s)	IRSL (50 °C; 200s)	IRSL (50 °C; 200s)
4	Test dose (17Gy)	IRSL (290 °C; 200s)	IRSL (225 °C; 200s)
5	Cutheat (180 °C)	Test dose	Test dose
6	Blue OSL (125 °C; 40s)	Preheat (320 °C; 60s)	Preheat (250 °C; 60s)
7	Blue OSL (280 °C; 40s)	IRSL (50 °C; 200s)	IRSL (50 °C; 200s)
8		IRSL (290 °C; 200s)	IRSL (225 °C; 200s)
9		IRSL (325 °C; 100s)	IRSL (290 °C; 100s)

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942 **Table 1.** Flowchart of the SAR-OSL measurements on quartz (Murray and Wintle,
943 2000, 2003), pIRIR₂₉₀ (Thiel et al., 2011a; Buylaert et al., 2011a, 2012) and pIRIR
944 (Buylaert et al., 2009; Wacha and Frechen, 2011; Vasiliniuc et al., 2012) protocols
945 applied in this study.

sample code	stratigraphic unit	depth (cm)	Equivalent dose			Radionuclide concentration			Random error error			Systematic error			Total dose rate			Age (ka)		
			4-11 μm quartz	pIRIR ₂₂₅ pfg	pIRIR ₂₉₀ pfg	K-40	Th-232	Ra-226	4-11 μm quartz	pIRIR ₂₂₅ pfg	pIRIR ₂₉₀ pfg	4-11 μm quartz	pIRIR ₂₂₅ pfg	pIRIR ₂₉₀ pfg	4-11 μm quartz	pIRIR ₂₂₅ pfg	pIRIR ₂₉₀ pfg	4-11 μm quartz	pIRIR ₂₂₅ pfg	pIRIR ₂₉₀ pfg
XY 40	L1	40	82±2	88±2	96±3	555±6	55±5	30±1	3.2	3.6	3.9	8.7	8.3	8.3	3.7±0.10	4.1±0.12	4.1±0.12	22±2	21±2	23±2
XY 100	L1	100	121±1	135±4	143±3	534±5	51±3	28±1	2.2	3.3	2.8	8.7	8.3	8.3	3.5±0.07	3.9±0.08	3.9±0.08	35±3	35±3	37±3
XY 180	L1	180	201±5	22±4	236±3	573±6	56±1	35±1	2.8	2.0	1.5	8.9	8.5	8.5	3.9±0.01	4.3±0.05	4.3±0.05	52±5	53±5	55±5
XY 260	L1	260	249±4	310±5	308±4	516±9	62±3	40±1	2.6	2.6	2.4	9.4	8.9	8.9	3.9±0.08	4.5±0.09	4.5±0.09	64±6	70±6	69±6
XY 340	S1/L1	340	347±6	471±14	604±37	582±6	57±1	30±0.2	1.9	3.1	6.2	8.8	8.4	8.4	3.8±0.03	4.2±0.03	4.2±0.03	92±8	118±10	143±15
XY 400	S1	400	403±13	586±24	761±45	610±6	55±1	27±2	3.3	4.3	6.0	8.6	8.3	8.3	3.7±0.04	4.2±0.05	4.2±0.05	108±10	140±13	182±19
XY 460	L2/S1	460	401±9	614±20	799±25	496±7	54±1	28±1	2.4	3.4	3.3	9	8.6	8.6	3.4±0.03	3.8±0.04	3.8±0.04	119±11	162±15	211±19
XY 575	L2	575	474±10	798±23	888±49	488±6	54±1	33±1	2.3	2.9	5.6	9.2	8.7	8.7	3.4±0.03	3.9±0.03	3.9±0.03	138±13	205±19	228±24

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947 **Table 2.** Summary of the SAR-OSL, pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ ages. The age uncertainties were determined following **Aitken and**
948 **Allred (1972)**. The uncertainties associated with the luminescence and dosimetry data are random; the uncertainties mentioned on
949 the optical ages are the overall uncertainties. The systematic errors taken into account include: 2% beta source calibration, 3%
950 conversion factors, 5% attenuation and etching factors, 3% gamma spectrometer calibration, 15% cosmic radiation, 25% water
951 content. All uncertainties represent 1 σ . Specific activities were measured using gamma spectrometry and the ages were determined
952 considering 15% water content; adopted alpha efficiency factor was 0.04±0.02 for 4-11 μm quartz and 0.08±0.02 for polymineral 4-11

953 μm fine grains, respectively (**Rees-Jones, 1995**). The contribution of cosmic radiation was taken into account and calculated
954 accordingly to **Prescott and Hutton (1994)**.

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Sample code	aliq	g-value (%/decade)	Average g-value (%/decade)
XY 40	aliq 1	-0.97±-0.59	0.31±0.58
	aliq 2	-0.83±-0.60	
	aliq 3	4.22±0.56	
	aliq 4	0.31±0.58	
XY100	aliq 1	0.02±0.58	0.07±0.27
	aliq 2	-0.20±-0.62	
	aliq 3	0.84±0.60	
	aliq 4	-0.40±-0.59	
XY340	aliq 1	-2.47±-0.87	0.62±1.03
	aliq 2	1.43±0.91	
	aliq 3	1.71±0.92	
	aliq 4	1.81±0.94	
	aliq 2	3.11±0.96	
	aliq 3	1.18±0.97	
	aliq 4	1.88±0.98	

959 **Table 3.** Fading rates measured on polymineral fine grains using pIRIR₂₂₅ protocol.

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Supplementary material

Table S1. Measured equivalent doses using SAR-OSL protocol along with the results of the intrinsic tests (Recycling, IR depletion and Recuperation).

Sample code	aliq	Equivalent dose (Gy)	Recycling	IR depletion	Recuperation (%)
XY 40	10	82±2	0.97±0.01	0.98±0.01	0.06±0.01
XY 100	10	121±1	0.97±0.01	0.98±0.01	0.05±0.01
XY 180	15	201±5	0.97±0.01	0.96±0.01	0.11±0.01
XY 260	14	249±4	0.97±0.01	0.98±0.01	0.08±0.01
XY 340	10	347±6	0.97±0.01	0.97±0.01	0.10±0.01
XY 400	10	403±13	0.98±0.01	0.97±0.01	0.09±0.01
XY 460	10	401±9	0.97±0.01	0.98±0.01	0.08±0.01
XY 575	10	473±10	0.98±0.01	0.99±0.01	0.08±0.01

Table S2. The measured equivalent doses along with the performance parameters of 4-11 μm polymineral grains using pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ protocols. The number of aliquots (n) averaged for equivalent dose calculation is also given. Quoted errors represent 1σ .

Sample code	Protocol	n	Equivalent dose (Gy)	Recycling	Recuperation (%)
XY 40	pIRIR ₂₂₅	10	90 \pm 2	1.02 \pm 0.01	1.5 \pm 0.21
	pIRIR ₂₉₀	10	100 \pm 2	0.98 \pm 0.01	1.4 \pm 0.25
XY 100	pIRIR ₂₂₅	10	137 \pm 4	0.97 \pm 0.01	0.9 \pm 0.11
	pIRIR ₂₉₀	10	150 \pm 2	1.00 \pm 0.02	1.3 \pm 0.17
XY 180	pIRIR ₂₂₅	10	232 \pm 4	1.00 \pm 0.01	1.1 \pm 0.10
	pIRIR ₂₉₀	10	245 \pm 3	0.97 \pm 0.01	1.2 \pm 0.08
XY 260	pIRIR ₂₂₅	10	315 \pm 5	0.99 \pm 0.01	1.2 \pm 0.07
	pIRIR ₂₉₀	9	316 \pm 4	1.00 \pm 0.02	1.2 \pm 0.12
XY 340	pIRIR ₂₂₅	10	475 \pm 14	0.97 \pm 0.02	0.9 \pm 0.07
	pIRIR ₂₉₀	10	617 \pm 37	0.96 \pm 0.02	1.1 \pm 0.10
XY 400	pIRIR ₂₂₅	12	590 \pm 24	0.93 \pm 0.01	0.7 \pm 0.06
	pIRIR ₂₉₀	9	774 \pm 45	0.95 \pm 0.02	0.9 \pm 0.10
XY 460	pIRIR ₂₂₅	10	619 \pm 20	0.94 \pm 0.01	0.6 \pm 0.04
	pIRIR ₂₉₀	8	814 \pm 25	0.99 \pm 0.01	0.9 \pm 0.12
XY 575	pIRIR ₂₂₅	15	807 \pm 23	0.97 \pm 0.01	0.4 \pm 0.05
	pIRIR ₂₉₀	8	907 \pm 49	0.95 \pm 0.01	0.8 \pm 0.15

Table S3. Measured residual doses using pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ procedures for (4-11 μ m) polymineral fine grains for each sample investigated here. Three or five aliquots from each sample were exposed to light for one month and then the residual dose was measured in the usual manner (same measurement protocol as for equivalent dose determination described in **Table 1**). The aliquots with poor recycling ratio (exceeding 10% from unity) were rejected.

Sample code	Protocol	n	Residual dose (Gy)
XY 40	pIRIR ₂₂₅	5	2.5±0.3
	pIRIR ₂₉₀	3	4.1±0.9
XY 100	pIRIR ₂₂₅	5	1.7±0.1
	pIRIR ₂₉₀	5	6.6±1.2
XY 180	pIRIR ₂₂₅	5	3.9±0.4
	pIRIR ₂₉₀	5	8.7±0.7
XY260	pIRIR ₂₂₅	5	4.9±0.6
	pIRIR ₂₉₀	5	8.3±0.9
XY 340	pIRIR ₂₂₅	5	3.4±0.6
	pIRIR ₂₉₀	5	12.5±1.4
XY 400	pIRIR ₂₂₅	5	3.6±0.6
	pIRIR ₂₉₀	5	13.5±1.5
XY 460	pIRIR ₂₂₅	5	4.7±0.5
	pIRIR ₂₉₀	5	15.5±2.0
XY 575	pIRIR ₂₂₅	5	8.8±1.0
	pIRIR ₂₉₀	5	19.0±2.6

Figure S1. Results of the fading measurements on individual aliquots of 4-11 μm polymineral material using pIRIR₂₂₅ protocol. The signals were read after a maximum delay of 50 days for samples XY40 and XY100 while for sample XY340 the maximum delay was

2 days. A number of 4 consecutive prompt read-outs were carried out before signal measurement after delay and two consecutive prompts read-outs were further added after different delays times.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationship that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.